

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies / IPBES transformative change assessment

Relevant records from search 1 on institutional fit and spatial fit

Bergsten, A., D. Galafassi, and Ö. Bodin. 2014. "The Problem of Spatial Fit in Social-Ecological Systems: Detecting Mismatches between Ecological Connectivity and Land Management in an Urban Region." *Ecology and Society* 19 (4). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-06931-190406>.

Brown, K. 2003. "Integrating Conservation and Development: A Case of Institutional Misfit." *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 1 (9): 479–87. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295\(2003\)001\[0479:ICADAC\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2003)001[0479:ICADAC]2.0.CO;2).

Ebbin, Syma A, Alf H. Hoel, and Are K. Sydnes, eds. 2005. *A Sea Change: The Exclusive Economic Zone and Governance Institutions for Living Marine Resources*. Springer.

Ekstrom, J.A., and B.I. Crona. 2017. "Institutional Misfit and Environmental Change: A Systems Approach to Address Ocean Acidification." *Science of the Total Environment* 576: 599–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.114>.

Håkon Hoel, Alf, Are K. Sydnes, and Syma A Ebbin. 2005. "Ocean Governance and Institutional Change." In *A Sea Change: The Exclusive Economic Zone and Governance Institutions for Living Marine Resources*, edited by Syma A Ebbin, Alf Håkon Hoel, and Are K. Sydnes. Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Springer.